

Influence of Guidance Services on Grief Management among selected Widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

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Abstract

The study was carried out to examine Influence of Guidance Services on Grief Management among selected Widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Three objectives, research questions and hypotheses were formulated. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 272 widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The sample for this study consisted of all the entire population of 272. Data for the study were collected by means of structured questionnaire titled "influence of guidance counselling services and grief management scale" (IGCSGMS)". The IGCSGMS was a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent to Very Low Extent. The instrument was validated by two experts, one in measurement and evaluation and the other in Guidance and Counselling. Cronbach Alpha was used for the reliability test which yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.86, 0.75, and 0.88 respectively. 272 Copies of questionnaire were distributed, and (two hundred and sixty-eight) 268 copies were retrieved for analysis. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. Z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that Information service plays a crucial role in influencing grief management among widows by providing timely and relevant information that can help them navigate their loss. Based on the findings, recommendations were made among which was that Government should support guidance and counseling practically by providing and making funds available for all the services in guidance and counselling.

Keywords: Influence, Guidance Services, Grief Management, Widows

INTRODUCTION

The death of a spouse is one of the most stressful events a person may experience during a lifetime (Mabunda & Ross, 2023). Death is a universal and unique reality that every individual goes through that cannot be avoided regardless of age, academic qualification, race, gender or social status nor delayed in the human experience. Every individual has to confront death at some point in their life, whether it is the death of a loved one; spouse etc. Death is an experience that transcends cultural, social and economic boundaries. For many, death arrives as an unwelcomed event. It is certain that every individual will experience it but uncertain in the time or manner by which it will occur. Most of the times, death comes unannounced which may leave the bereaved dis comforted and psychologically derailed. It is therefore crucial to expose them to guidance counselling services to alleviate the impact of the grief.

Counselling is described as the process of helping people with their problems. It is defined in which one person (the counsellor) assists another person or group of persons (client/counselee) in a person-to-person or face-to-face encounter. The assistance may take many forms. It may be educational, vocational, social, recreational, emotional and or moral. Effective counselling thus aims at achieving a set goal, result in terms of changing the lives of people with problems (Nwonyuku, 2017)). The definition of counselling clearly shows that counselling

can help widows adjust and cope with their stressful situations. This might be the reason why some researchers have carried out a study on the plight of widows and counselling strategies and or needs.

Counselling is the process of assisting an individual such as widow-lecturers with their concern to effect a positive change. Counselling has its main goal as helping clients learn to cope with problems of living. It has varied intervention strategies that could be employed to address positive life adjustment of widows (Nwaoba & Uba, n.d). In adopting appropriate guidance counselling service for widows, the following services are vital in checking the incidences of widowhood. Such services include, appraisal, information, counseling, placement, orientation, referral and evaluation.

Grief counselling is under intense scrutiny, but it continues to gain support from clients who have felt its effects first hand (Macias, Jones, Harvey, Barreira, Harding and Rodican 2020). The techniques in grief counseling are innovative and allow for growth and individuality to flourish. In the new millennium no doubt there will be even more room for expansion, and a new set of quantitative data that will better represent the effectiveness of the grief counseling movement on the clients of the future. Grief is the anguish experienced after significant loss, usually the death of a beloved person. Grief often includes physiological distress, separation anxiety, confusion, yearning, obsessive

dwelling on the past, and apprehension about the future, (Tateo, 2023).

Shear and Gribbin (2017) defines grief counselling as “a type of counseling designed to help individuals with complicated grief reactions, particularly those that interfere with their ability to function in daily life.” Shear’s definition emphasizes grief counseling focus on individuals experiencing complicated grief reactions. The goal is to address grief responses that significantly impact an individual’s daily functioning, providing support and strategies to alleviate their distress. The renowned psychologist (Worden, 2021) further maintains that the primary objectives of counselling in grief management are; accepting the loss, working through the pain, adjusting to life and maintaining a connection.

Grief management, often provided through grief counseling, aims to support individuals through their grief journey and facilitate healthy adaptation to loss. Grief counseling offers a structured and empathetic approach to help bereaved individuals process their emotions, understand their grief reactions, and develop coping mechanisms to navigate the challenges of bereavement. Understanding the effectiveness of grief counseling is crucial for mental health professionals to provide optimal support to bereaved individuals and enhance their healing and resilience.

Appraisal is a service that is designed to gather, analyze, and utilize various personal, psychological, and social data about clients to gain a better understanding of them (Umoh, 2014). It is assumed that with the increasing complexities surrounding bereaved client, they find it difficult to adjust themselves to the environment, the society expectations, and satisfactory family roles. Through the appraisal services, the widows’ unique challenges are identified, they also understand themselves including their strengths and weakness which enables them to get insight into their circumstances.

Information services are vital services in facilitating a rational planning on personal social goals and life generally. Doka (2017) holds that the information service of a counsellor aims at making data on opportunities, personal and career issues available to clients to enable them make choices and decisions that are authentic, suitable and responsible. By this service, bereaved persons could be aided in making choices to further in their career path, thereby helping to get along

with the situation at hand. Counsellors are able to disseminate information on educational and career materials to client through the information service (Adoga, 2020). Additionally, these services will afford widows where to go to obtain help and lay them complains such as human rights commission, non-governmental organization.

Placement service is another form of guidance service that is needed for aggrieved client for proper adjustment. In this context, a placement service could be referred to as the process of helping a widow to enter and make adjustment in the next stage of life development. This counselling service is described as personalized in the sense that usually, the problem brought by a widow is private in nature and requires some emphatic, confidentiality and warm atmosphere, such problems may include emotional problems, self-concept problems, issues of depression, loss of self-worth, esteem, dignity, shame, anger which required counselling. These services are regarded as the heart of guidance services, since it provides a forum for interaction, a link between the widow and the counselor. This next step adjustment may involve steps towards further personal social adjustment into appropriate medical treatment and vocational skills training.

Counselling has been used to designate a wide range of procedures comprising advice giving, support in times of trouble or need, encouragement, information giving, and test interpretation (Rushahu, 2017). Counselling is a process by which a person is assisted to behave in a more rewarding manner. Counselling is viewed as a personalized, intimate interview or dialogue between a person experiencing some emotional, social, educational, physical, and vocational problems and a professional counselor (Egunjobi, 2019). It can also be seen as a service that helps individual to solve problems and learn to cope with these problems that are not easy to solve. This is why the special needs population can be focused so that they are assisted out of their needs. Counselling is designed to remove the emotional, psychological and personal social roadblocks placed in the way of an individual by the multidimensional problems of the day-to-day life (Oluka & Okorie, 2014). Counseling helps clients by bringing much-needed change to their lives. When successful, counseling offers the client the opportunity to change by establishing specific goals, improving their coping skills, promoting decision making, and improving relationships across life domains (Senyah, 2021).

The involvement of counselling with grieving widows therefore is to improve, manage and possibly remedy the challenges, facing them. The educational challenges facing this category of people are quite obvious and they need new strategies in resolving through counselling.

Widowhood is a phenomenon or condition a widow or widower undergoes after the death of a spouse. Widowhood experiences for a woman irrespective of age at bereavement has a wide array of destabilizing effect on a widow's emotional and psychological well-being that can lead to mental health issues, such as depression, anxiety, frustration and others. Oladejo (2022) researched the stress and counselling needs among widows in Saki West Local Government, Oyo State. Also, Senyah (2021) worked on the Quality of Life, Psychological Distress and Adjustment Strategies Among Young Widows in Kumasi Sub-Metropolitan District Councils: Implications for Counselling. Similarly, Nwanozie (2023) conducted a study on Impact of widowhood on psychological wellbeing and quality of life of spouses in Onitsha, Anambra State. In addition, Bala (2015) investigated the plight and adjustment strategies of widows in Danko Wasagu Local Government Area of Kebbi State. Furthermore, Iruloh and Elsie (2018) examined adjustment strategies of widows to widowhood stress based on their age, in Rivers State, Nigeria. Nonetheless, Muhammed (2020) studied the psychosocial needs of bereaved spouses in Nigeria: implications for grief counseling intervention. It can be concluded from the earlier studies that much more attention has been given to counselling needs and adjustment/coping strategies of widows. However, for widows to benefit maximally from counselling, there is need for counsellors to understand the various sources and natures of widowhood stress. It was against this background that this study was designed to investigate Influence of Guidance Services on Grief Management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

The death of a husband makes the wife lose some of her pride and glory, especially positions assumed after the husband's status. She becomes an object of maltreatment. The widow's status traditionally changes from womanhood to widowhood. The pathetic state of widows is often worsened by some cultural expectations, norms and deprivations. Seeking guidance services can help to separate realistic from unrealistic guilt by asking questions during the recoil stage, where many widows

are not prepared for the negative feelings that are experienced.

As a result, some widows do not seek for counselling services in order to cope with their state of widowhood and that has diverse challenges such as depressive episodes, isolation and low self-esteem. Researches done showed that generally, some women do not seek for counselling services like men. This calls for guidance services to be rendered to them for proper adjustment so they can carry on with life like every other person in society. This study used information service, appraisal service, placement services and orientation services, to investigate the influence of guidance services on grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of guidance counselling on grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the extent to which information service influence grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. ascertain the extent to which referral service influence grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State
3. examine the extent to which appraisal service influence grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the study.

1. To what extent does information service influence grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?
2. To what extent does referral service influence grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?
3. To what extent does appraisal service influence grief management among widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study, which were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of educated and uneducated widows on the extent to which information service influences grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of educated and uneducated widows on the extent to which referral service influences grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of educated and uneducated widows on the extent to which appraisal service influences grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research was adopted for this study. The area of study was Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of 272 widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis. 101 educated widows and 171 uneducated widows from different associations in Port Harcourt. The sample for this study consisted of all the entire population of 272 widows. Census sampling techniques was used for the study because it is a manageable one and the researcher felt it is good enough for the study.

The instrument for data collection for this study is researcher-structured questionnaire titled “Guidance Counselling Services and Grief Management Scale (GCSGMS)”. It is a single instrument having two sections and subscale Section A and B. Section A elicited personal information of the respondents while section B elicited information needed to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. This section required the respondents to respond to items by checking (√) where appropriate. The instrument was designed in rating scale format with the following options: Very High

Extent = 4, High Extent=3, Low Extent=2, Very Low Extent =1. The instrument was subjected to close scrutiny by two experts, one in Measurement and Evaluation and the other from Guidance and Counselling, all in Rivers State University.

Their validation established the content and face validities of the instrument for data collection. A test of internal consistency was carried out using Cronbach Alpha method to establish the reliability of the instrument, which gave a reliability coefficients of (r) 0.86, 0.75, and 0.88, for the three subscales of the instrument. Out of the 272 copies administered, 268 copies were successfully retrieved and valid for use in the study. These 268 responses were the one used for data analysis. Data collected for this study was analyzed using descriptive statistics involving mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Decision for acceptance and rejection was made by the researcher based on the criterion means of 2.50. That is, any mean response with 2.50 and above was rated “High Extent” while mean response below 2.50 was rated “Low Extent”. Decision for hypothesis testing was based on the fact that if the z-calculated was higher than the table or critical z-value, the hypothesis was rejected and if the z-calculated was lower than the z-critical value, the hypothesis was not rejected.

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent does Information Services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on how Information Service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis (N = 268)

S/N	Item Statements	Educated widows = 119			Uneducated widows = 149		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remarks	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1	Information services rendered by counsellors can aid widows in reducing the sense of destigmatization during grief	3.71	0.52	High extent	3.14	1.02	High extent
2	Information services play a crucial role among widows by providing timely and relevant information that can assist them navigate their track after bereaved	3.26	1.00	High extent	3.55	0.73	High extent
3	Information services provided by counsellor can assists widows to develop high aspirations afterward.	3.29	1.01	High extent	3.72	0.66	High extent
4	Information services promote awareness and education about the normalcy of grief and the benefits of counselling.	2.94	0.87	High extent	3.15	0.95	High extent

5	Information services could help widows to understand their strength and weakness so that they make realistic occupational decision during grief.	3.72	0.70	High extent	3.19	0.95	High extent
Total Mean		16.92	4.1		16.75	4.31	
Grand Mean & SD =		3.38	0.82		3.35	0.86	

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

The results in table 1 show that all the items on the table were rated to be high extent by the educated widows and uneducated widows. The respondents indicated among others that at high extent information services provided by counsellors can contribute to the destigmatization of seeking help for grief. Also, information services play a crucial role in influencing grief management among widows by providing timely and relevant information that can help them navigate their loss at high extent. The

confirmation was made with a grand mean of 3.38 and standard deviation of 0.82 for educated widows while that of uneducated widows were 3.35 and 0.86 for mean and standard deviation.

Research Question 2: To what extent does referral services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 4.2: Mean and Standard Deviation on how Guidance Counselling Influence the Grief Management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis (N = 268)

S/N	Item Statements	Educated widows = 119			Uneducated widows = 149		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remarks	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
6	Counsellor could enhance widows access to expertise who specialize in grief counselling	3.03	1.10	High Extent	3.35	0.90	High Extent
7	Receiving a referral from a counsellor can make individuals feel more comfortable seeking help	3.01	1.21	High Extent	2.86	1.23	High Extent
8	Referral services often vet counselors, ensuring that individuals receive quality care from licensed and experienced professionals	2.56	0.91	High Extent	3.36	0.85	High Extent
9	Referral services provide information about support groups or community resources, offering a broader support network.	2.68	0.82	High Extent	3.11	1.00	High Extent
10	Some referral services take into account personal preferences and needs, helping individuals find a counselor who aligns with their specific situation.	3.73	0.68	High Extent	3.06	0.98	High Extent
Total Mean =		15.01	4.63		15.74	4.96	
Grand Mean & SD =		3.00	0.92		3.14	0.99	

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

The results in Table 2 show that one of the items on the table were rated to a high extent (that is, item 6,7,8, and 9) while one of the items were rated to a very high extent (that is, item 10). At high extent, the respondents indicated that at high extent receiving a referral from a counsellor can make individuals feel more comfortable seeking help. The confirmation was made with a grand

mean of 3.00 and 0.92 while standard deviation of 3.14 and 0.99 for both educated widows and uneducated widows.

Research Question 3: To what extent does Appraisal Services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 4.3: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on How Appraisal Services Influence the Grief Management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis (N = 268)

S/N	Item Statements	Educated widows = 119			Uneducated widows = 149		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remarks	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
11	Appraisal counseling provides a safe space for widows to express their feelings, helping them process their grief more effectively	3.61	0.77	High extent	2.45	0.97	High extent
12	Appraisal counselling can help validate the emotions that widows experience, normalizing their grief and reducing feelings of isolation.	3.47	0.85	High extent	3.52	0.68	High extent
13	These services can equip widows with practical coping strategies and tools to manage their grief, leading to healthier emotional processing.	3.56	0.83	High extent	3.56	0.73	High extent
14	Appraisal counseling can offer personalized advice based on individual circumstances, making the support more relevant and effective.	3.35	0.90	High extent	3.03	0.81	High extent
15	Through counseling, widows can develop resilience, which can aid in their long-term adjustment and recovery.	3.23	0.97	High extent	3.07	1.03	High extent
Total Mean		17.22	4.32		15.63	4.22	
Grand Mean & SD =		3.44	0.86		3.12	0.84	

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

The result in table 3 shows that item 11,12,13,14 and 15 on the table were rated to a high extent. The grand mean of 3.44 and 3.12 brings the conclusion that appraisal services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of educated widows and uneducated widows on how information service influences the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 6: z-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Information service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	Std Error	p	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Educated widows	119	3.38	0.82					
Uneducated widows	149	3.35	0.86	0.011	0.05	0.3	1.96	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

From the z – test in Table 6, the calculated value is 0.3 while the z – critical value is 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. The z–calculated value is lower than z–critical value, the null hypothesis is therefore Accepted. Indicating there is no significant difference between the mean responses of educated widows and uneducated widows on how information service influences the Grief

management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Referral Service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 7: z-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Referral Service influence the Grief management among s selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	Std Error	p	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Educated widows	119	3.00	0.92	0.013	0.05	1.27	1.96	Accepted
Uneducated widows	1.49	3.14	0.99					

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

Table 7, the z-calculated value of 1.27 is less than z-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance and 266 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis is accepted. Indicating there is no significant difference between the mean responses of educated widows and uneducated widows on how referral service influences the grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Appraisal Service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Table 8: z-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Appraisal Service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	Std Error	p	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Educated widows	119	3.44	0.86	0.011	0.05	3.2	1.96	rejected
Uneducated widows	1.49	3.12	0.84					

Source: Field Survey, 2024

From the z-test in table 8, the z-calculated value of 3.2 is greater than z-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 levels of significance and 266 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis is rejected. Indicating there is a significant difference between the mean responses of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Appraisal Service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

calculated value of 0.3 which was less than z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding is in line with the view of Barros-Laneet al (2024), opined that the Information services play a crucial role in influencing grief management among widows by providing timely and relevant information that can help them navigate their loss. These services offer resources on coping strategies, support groups, and counseling options, making it easier for widows to find the help they need. For instance, digital platforms and online communities provide immediate access to grief management resources, allowing widows to connect with others who are experiencing similar losses and to learn from shared experiences. This connectivity can mitigate feelings of isolation and provide a sense of community and understanding.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion in this study was done according to each research question as thus:

Extent on how Information services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Findings on research question 1 on table 1 revealed that Information services contribute to the destigmatization of seeking help for grief. Information services play a crucial role in influencing grief management among widows by providing timely and relevant information that can help them navigate their loss with a grand mean of 3.38 from educated widows and 3.35 for uneducated widows. Hypothesis 1 on table 5 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of educated widows and uneducated widows on how information Services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, with z-

The findings on Abiolu, (2023) opined that information services can bridge the gap between widows and professional counseling services. By disseminating information about the availability and benefits of grief counseling, these services encourage widows to seek professional help. They also provide critical information on how to access these services, including details about local counselors, hotlines, and virtual counseling options. This can be particularly beneficial in rural areas where access to mental health services may be limited.

The availability of information in various formats, such as brochures, websites, and mobile apps, ensures that widows can find support in a manner that is convenient and accessible to them. By promoting awareness and education about the normalcy of grief and the benefits of counseling, these services can help change societal attitudes that may otherwise discourage widows from seeking help. Educational campaigns and informational resources can dispel myths and misconceptions about grief and mental health, making it more acceptable for widows to pursue professional support. Consequently, widows who have access to comprehensive information services are more likely to engage in effective grief management practices, leading to better emotional and psychological outcomes.

Extent Referral Services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Findings on research question 2 on table 2 revealed that counsellor helps widows to live peacefully with their fellow widows of different culture and religion with a grand mean of 3.00 for educated widows and 3.14 for uneducated widows. Hypothesis 2 on table 6 showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Referral Service influence the Grief management among some selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, with z-calculated value of 1.27 which was less than z-critical value of ± 1.96 . This finding is in line with the view of Idowu, 2014, opined that Referral Service is the transferring a widows to another professional counsellor or agency where their problem can be appropriately handled. These services are the fundamental basis of counselling programmes (Idowu, 2014). In line with the view of Nwonyuku, (2017), stated that Referral service affords the counsellor an opportunity to refer the cases which he cannot handle to specialists like clinical psychologist, medical practitioner and others. Referral Services are beyond the capability of the school counsellor or guidance teacher, it is important to establish a referral network. This should consist of a team of well trained and skilled professionals who have expertise in assisting referred individuals, Referral does not imply the helper might have failed, but signifies strength on the part of the helper, who recognizes his limitations, and explores opportunities to maximize the help he/she can offer.

Extent Appraisal Services influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Findings on research question 3 on table 3 revealed that Counsellors always encourage widows to discover new ways of doing things with a grand mean of 3.44 for educated widows and 3.12 for uneducated widows. Hypothesis 3 on table 7 showed that that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of educated widows and uneducated widows on how Appraisal Service influence the Grief management among selected widows in Port Harcourt Metropolis, with z-calculated value of 3.2 which was greater than z-critical value of ± 1.96 . The findings support the view of Ngozi (n.d) who stated that appraisal services of guidance and counselling affords the counsellors the opportunity of having insight into the strength and weakness of widows. In line with the view of Ngozi (n.d). Opined that appraisal services involve the use of tests and non-test instrument to collect, analyze and interpret data for widows to understand themselves better. It also affords counsellors and significant others the opportunity of having insight into the strength and weakness of widows. He further depicts that Information from appraisal services can be used for different educational purposes. In agreement with Perkins (2016) opined that appraisal of an individual is the value judgment arrived at, based on the result of the assessment of various relevant characteristics of the person. It involves the collection of data, analysis of subjective and objective personal and psychological data about widows. This gives a full understanding of these widows and how they can be helped.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data analysis in the study, findings and discussion were made. The researcher concluded that information services contribute to the destigmatization of seeking help for grief. Information services play a crucial role in influencing grief management among widows by providing timely and relevant information that can help them navigate their loss. The researcher also concluded that counsellor helps widows to live peacefully with their fellow widows of different culture and religion. Counsellors always encourage widows to discover new ways of doing things.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made;

- i. Government should support guidance and counseling practically by providing and making

- funds available for all the services in guidance and counseling.
- ii. Counselors in Nigeria should help individuals to improve by using Appraisal service, placement service, orientation service, and or a combination of both.
- iii. Government should help to train and appoint qualified guidance counselors to help meet with the widow's problems.

REFERENCES

- Abiolu, O. A. (2023). Widows and their information-seeking behavior in south-western Nigeria. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Abiolu, O. A. (2023). Widows and their information-seeking behavior in south-western Nigeria. *Library Philosophy & Practice*.
- Adoga, R. O. (2020). The newness of guidance and counselling practices in schools. *International Journal of Educational Research and Policy Making*.
- Bala Ribah, A. I. S. H. A. (2015). Plight and adjustment strategies of widows in Danko.
- Barros-Lane, L., Alvarez-Rodriguez, V., Cornelius, V. E., & Smith, V. D. (2024). "Grief lasts longer than sympathy": Qualitatively examining disenfranchised grief in young widowhood. *Journal of Loss and Trauma*, 1-22
- Doka, K. J. (2017). Disenfranchised grief and trauma. In *Handbook of Traumatic Loss*. Routledge Printing Press.
- Egunjobi, R. A. (2013). Virtual library for persons with special education needs. In O. R. Ernstmeier, K. Christman, & E. (Eds.), *Grief and Loss* [Internet]. Chippewa Valley Technical College.
- Idowu, A. I. (2014). Raising the bar: The counsellors' mandate.
- Iruloh, B. N., & Elsie, W. (2018). Adjustment strategies of widows to widowhood stress based on their age: The case of Rivers State, Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 6(1), 76-91.
- Mabunda, Y. P., & Ross, E. (2023). Experiences of Black South African widows regarding mourning rituals following the death of their spouses: Upholding cultural practices or violating human rights? *Death Studies*, 47(3), 328-338
- Macias, C., Jones, D., Harvey, J., Barreira, P., Harding, C., & Rodican, C. (2004). Bereavement in the context of serious mental illness. *Psychiatric Services*, 55(4), 421-426
- Muhammed, S. A. (2020). Psychosocial needs of bereaved spouses in Nigeria: Implications for grief counselling intervention. *Canadian Journal of Family and Youth*, 12(3), 78-97.
- Ngozi, I. P. (n.d). Impact of guidance services on the career choice of secondary school students in public secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria
- Nwanozie, D. S. (2023). Impact of widowhood on psychological wellbeing and quality of life of spouses in Onitsha, Anambra State. *Journal of Psychology and Behavioural Disciplines, COOU*, 3(1).
- Nwaoba, C. N., Ajoku, M. U., & Uba, M. B. I. Perception of university widow lecturers and counsellors in South-East Nigeria on life adjustment of the widows.
- Nwonyuku, K. (2017). Impact of guidance and counseling on performance of secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.
- Oladejo, K. O., & Mukaila, K. A. (2022). Sources, nature of stress, and counselling needs among widows in Saki West Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Professional Counseling*, 5(1), 116-128
- Oluka, B. N., & Okorie, G. O. (2014). Impacts of counselling on people with special educational needs. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 4(6), 97-100.
- Perkins, J. M., Lee, H. Y., James, K. S., Oh, J., Krishna, A., Heo, J. & Subramanian, S. V. (2016). Marital status, widowhood duration, gender, and health outcomes: A cross-sectional study among older adults in India. *BMC Public Health*, 16, 1-12.
- Rushahu, B. G. (2017). *Guidance and counselling services to students with disabilities in higher learning institutions in Tanzania: Practices and*

- implications* (Doctoral dissertation, Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg).
- Senyah, A. B. (2021). *Quality of life, psychological distress and adjustment strategies among young widows in Kumasi Sub-Metropolitan District Councils: Implications for counselling* (Doctoral dissertation, UCC).
- Shear, M. K., & Gribbin Bloom, C. (2017). Complicated grief treatment: An evidence-based approach to grief therapy. *Journal of Rational-Emotive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, 35, 6-25.
- Tateo, L. (2023). Cultural mediation of grief: The role of aesthetic experience. *Culture & Psychology*, 29(3), 411-433
- Umoh, I. S. (2014). Appraisal of guidance and counseling services in schools and non-school settings in Nigeria: The way forward. *Journal of Resourcefulness and Distinction*, 7(1).
- Worden, J. W., Kosminsky, P., & Carverhill, P. (2021). Foundational grief theories. *Handbook of thanatology: The essential body of knowledge for the study of death, dying, and bereavement*, 262-281.